

From FAIR Research Data to FAIR Government Information

19th International Digital Curation Conference

February 18, 2025

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Who we are...

- Deborah Yun Caldwell (UNT)
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Mission statement

OUR VISION

We imagine a world where government information is preserved and accessible for an engaged public and equitable democracy.

OUR MISSION

The PEGI Project advocates on behalf of current and future users of public information. Developing a community of practice to preserve and provide access to electronic government information is a large endeavor that will take many hands. Together, we seek to build capacity for libraries to preserve historically significant born-digital government information.

Initial activities

Word	Source	Definition	What's in	What's out
Publications	Government Publishing Office 44 USC §1901	"Government publication" ... means informational matter which is published as an individual document at Government expense, or as required by law." Note: GPO has one scope for Cataloging and Indexing, and a different scope for the FDLP. Further, in the FDLP, distribution is sometimes limited by depository or document type.	Things that look like "documents," as described in this scope note from GPO .	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publications of entities that do not receive Congressional appropriations and whose employees are not U.S. government employees, such as the Federal Reserve Bank system Records (as defined by NARA) Datasets / GIS data For official use / classified
Information resources	Office of Management and Budget OMB Circular A-130	"The requirements of this Circular apply to the information resources management activities of all agencies of the Executive Branch of the Federal Government. The requirements of this Circular apply to management activities concerning all information resources in any medium (unless otherwise noted), including paper and electronic information."	Agencies' public information resources regardless of format (electronic or print)	National security information and systems otherwise governed
Work of the U.S. Government, or Government work	Copyright Office 17 USC §105	A "work of the United States Government" is an otherwise copyrightable work (defined in 17 USC §102), prepared by an officer or employee of the United States Government as part of that person's official duties.	Works created by government employees at work	Information not produced by government employees or subject to other IP protection (e.g. contracted technical reports, patents, trademarks, databases). Potentially this same information outside of the U.S.
Records	National Archives and Records Administration 44 USC § 3301	Records are defined as "all recorded information, regardless of form or characteristics, made or received by a Federal agency under Federal law or in connection with the transaction of public business and preserved or appropriate for preservation by that agency or its legitimate successor as evidence of the organization, functions, policies, decisions, procedures, operations, or other activities of the United States Government or because of the informational value of data in them."	Records properly scheduled by an agency, or explicitly covered by legislation, e.g., Presidential Records Act, or materials voluntarily deposited, Center for Legislative Archives. Records released via Freedom of Information Act request	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Only 1-3% of what are considered, "records" are scheduled for permanent retention Does not include "library and museum material made or acquired and preserved solely for reference or exhibition purposes."
Datasets	Data.gov DCAT-US Schema v1.1, based on Project Open Data Metadata Schema	"A dataset is an identifiable collection of structured data objects unified by some criteria" and available in machine-readable format.	Federal agencies are required to post government datasets and APIs. The Open Data Points of Contact (POC) for each agency determines what should be included in its Data Inventory. Some documents are included that would not be considered typical datasets.	
Documents			Varies by local policy.	Varies by local policy.

Opportunity: FAIR Principles as a mechanism to apply to this context

Charting a FAIR Direction for the US Government Information Ecosystem

March 1, 2024

Continuing our exploration of research data management and its commonalities and overlaps with the wider government information sphere, we now turn to the potential application of the FAIR Principles as a framework to explore the ways in which government information may or may not meet public needs for current and future use.

- I. [FAIR Principles](#)
- II. [Federal Information Dissemination Practices](#)
- III. [How FAIR is Federal Information?](#)
- IV. [More FAIR Federal Information](#)
- V. [Concluding Thoughts and Next Steps](#)

FAIR Principles & the U.S. Government

- The U.S. Government is one of the largest publishers of information and research data in the world.
- FAIR Principles are increasingly part of federal agency practices.
 - OSTP Memos (2013, 2022)
 - Open Government Data Act (2018)
 - OMB, GAO recommendations
- All born-digital & digitally reformatted government information is itself data
- The vast majority of federal government information produced for public access is not published in a repository

Information Practices in Federal Agencies

FINDABLE

Some government repositories or databases may meet some criteria for findability but lack others

ACCESSIBLE

All publicly available federal databases can at a minimum be accessed by users over standard internet protocols

INTEROPERABLE

Resources in repositories are typically described with standardized metadata; broadly, interoperability is the exception

REUSABLE

Documentation can be thin. Majority of informational works are produced in standard formats, but typically lack technical provenance metadata

Our original plan...

Explore the application of the FAIR Principles as a framework to understand ways in which government information may or may not meet public needs for current and future use.

PRESERVATION OF ELECTRONIC
GOVERNMENT INFORMATION

PEGIPROJECT.ORG | @PEGIPROJECT

THE WHITE HOUSE

PRESIDENT DONALD J. TRUMP

AMERICA IS BACK

Where to go from here?

Who is responsible for the EoT crawl?

EoT is a [partnership](#) among the Internet Archive, not-for-profit organizations, and libraries. The PEGI Project is not an official partner of EoT but we celebrate their efforts to create a comprehensive snapshot of federal web content at the end of each presidential administration.

Can I contribute to the EoT crawl?

Yes! Individuals and groups are invited and encouraged to contribute. [The 2024 EoT Crawl is accepting nominations until the crawl ends](#), which is estimated to be late **spring 2025**. You can contribute individual URLs directly through their nomination tool, or you can submit bulk lists of URLs to the project. Keep in mind, building bulk lists is a great project for groups of people interested in spinning up "data rescue"-style events!

What kinds of websites can I look for to help with the EoT crawl?

In Scope: *Federal* government websites (.gov) in the Legislative, Executive, or Judicial branches of the U.S. government, and their related social media accounts.

- Federal government websites on other domains, such as .mil, .edu, and .com, including websites for federally-funded programs and projects, are also in scope. For example, the [SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory](#) is a public-private partnership between the Department of Education and Stanford University, with a website hosted on stanford.edu.
- The greatest priority this year is to identify and submit websites that are likely to change dramatically or disappear during or soon after the presidential administration transition in early 2025.

Out of Scope: Local or state government websites, and any other non-government sites including those documenting the U.S. elections.

What else can I do?

Stay tuned as we prepare to share information about additional projects and efforts that would benefit from your time and effort. Please contact us if you're working on a government information or data preservation project that needs public participation. And, if you see something out there and you're not sure if it's legitimate, feel free to reach out to us too. We'll do our best to help you untangle the truth.

Data Rescue 2.0

<https://www.datarescueproject.org>

[Home](#) [About](#) [Current Efforts](#) [Resources](#) [Contact](#)

About Us

The Data Rescue Project is a coordinated effort among a group of data organizations, including [IASSIST](#), [RDAP](#), and members of the [Data Curation Network](#). Our goal is to serve as a clearinghouse for data rescue-related efforts and data access points for public US governmental data that are currently at risk.

We want to know what is happening in the community so that we can coordinate focus. Efforts include: data gathering, data curation and cleaning, data cataloging, and providing sustained access and distribution of data assets.

[Current list of data rescue efforts and useful resources](#)

The Data Rescue community welcomes participation from people all over the world, and these members bring with them a wide variety of professional, personal, and social backgrounds; whatever these may be, we treat colleagues with dignity and respect.

Follow us on Bluesky: [@datarescueproject.org](#)

See something, save something!

Interested in joining our community? Take a look at the [Data Rescue Community Conduct and Contributions Guidelines](#) to get started.

Thank you.

Questions or Ideas? Contact us:

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